

2-Substituted-6-[(1'-substituted-3'-methylpyrazol-5'-yl)]-7-hydroxybenzoxazoles: All the N-phenyl pyrazolyl and pyrazolyl substituted benzoxazoles were prepared by taking equimolar proportions of chromonooxazole and phenylhydrazine or hydrazine hydrate in alcohol and refluxing and working out in the above manner.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Principal, Regional Engineering College, Warangal for facilities and Prof. S. R. Ramadas, Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras for valuable suggestions. One of the authors (M.S.S.) is thankful to the Principal, C. K. M. College, Warangal for encouragement. The authors are also grateful to Dr. M. A. Singaracharya, Lecturer, C. K. M. College, for kind help in testing antifungal and antibacterial activities.

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A Field Test for The Detection and Semiquantitative Determination of Sulphurdioxide in Air and Water

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Manuscript received 16 October 1981, revised 11 March 1982, accepted 1 May 1982

SULPHURDIOXIDE is a major pollutant originating from industrial and domestic emissions. It is also a major component of automobile exhaust and its applications as a preservative or fungicide are major sources of sulphurdioxide pollution. The "Threshold Limit Value" adopted by American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (1969) is 5 ppm¹. In view of its hazardous effects on health, vegetation and property², a fast and reliable method for detection of traces of sulphurdioxide would be of immense value.

In search of better organic bases to increase the intensity of brick red colouration in the Bodeker

reaction³, it was found that malonyldihydrazide (MDH) along with zinc acetate and sodium nitroprusside gives a very intense brick red precipitate in solution. The reaction is used for spot test to detect as low as 0.2 ppm sulphurdioxide in air or water.

Experimental

Preparation of malonyldihydrazide: Malonyldihydrazide was prepared by adding hydrazine hydrate (0.1 mole in alcohol) to an alcoholic solution of diethyl malonate (0.05 mole in alcohol) in 2:1 mole ratio. The white solid obtained was crystallised from water, m.p. 150°.

Reagents: (1) 1 M zinc acetate solution in 5% v/v glycerol, (2) 2% w/v solution of sodium nitroprusside in distilled water and (3) 2% w/v solution of malonyldihydrazide in distilled water were used.

Sulphurdioxide for air analysis was prepared from freshly prepared sodium sulphite solution in water with a small amount of HCl.

All reagents used were of A. R. grade.

Procedure

Spot test for the detection of sulphurdioxide as sulphite ions in water: 1 ml of each of the above mentioned reagents 1, 2 and 3 were taken in a 10 ml beaker serially. A cream coloured colloidal solution was formed. The solution was stable for a week. One drop of this solution was taken on a spot plate. One drop of sulphurdioxide solution (5 µg/ml) was added to this spot. A brick red precipitate formed immediately which indicated the presence of sulphurdioxide. The precipitate was stable for more than 24 hr.

Detection in air: Test papers were prepared and examined for the detection of traces of sulphurdioxide in air by the earlier reported method⁴ using 2% w/v solution of malonyldihydrazide along with 1 M zinc acetate solution and 2% sodium nitroprusside solution. The colour produced in the test paper was compared with that obtained from passing 1 litre of air containing 0.1 to 2 ppm of sulphurdioxide. A semiquantitative determination was possible.

Results and Discussion

The present method is more sensitive than the earlier reported methods. Brick red precipitate is not soluble in organic solvents like chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, butanol, methanol, ethanol, methyl acetate, etc. Precipitate is either decomposed or remains undissolved in these solvents.

Carbonate, chloride, sulphate, ammonia, nitrate, nitrite, phosphate did not interfere in this reaction. Sulphide ion was found to give similar colour reaction. However, the interference from sulphide ion can be eliminated by passing the air sample through mercuric chloride solution.

The pH of the coloured solution after the formation of the precipitate was found to be between 5.5–5.8. Increase in intensity of the colour by addition of malonyldihydrazide was supposed to be due to the formation of $[\text{Zn}(\text{MDH})_2]_2 \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot \text{NO} \cdot \text{SO}_3$. Following the described procedure, semi quantitative determination of sulphites in water is possible by comparing the colour of the precipitate produced by varying amounts of sulphites (0.1 to 2 ppm) with that produced by the unknown. Further studies to establish this reported reagent system as an absorbing reagent for sulphurdioxide are being pursued.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur, for necessary facilities.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Aromatic Amines Using Catechol and Iodine

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Manuscript received 16 October 1981, revised 9 February 1982,
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A new spectrophotometric method for the assay of primary and secondary aromatic amines with catechol-iodine reagent at pH 2.6 ± 0.6 has been developed. It is based on the development of purple-red colour of maximum absorbance (λ_{max} 500-520 nm) within 5-20 min (depending on the amine) after mixing with the reagent. The colour is stable for 2 hr. The method is simple, reproducible and accurate within $\pm 1.0\%$. It has been extended to the determination of drugs in pure and dosage forms which either contain a free primary aromatic amino group (sulpha drugs, local anaesthetics, dapsone) or release it through hydrolysis (succinyl sulphathiazole) or reduction (chloramphenicol or folic acid).

Experimental

The absorbance measurements were made with Shimadzu UV 140 double beam spectrophotometer

with 1 cm glass cells. The pH of the solution was adjusted to the desired value using an Elico model LI-120 digital pH meter. A freshly prepared 0.1% aqueous solution of catechol was used. Glycine-HCl (pH 1.0-2.1) and potassium acid phthalate-HCl buffers were prepared according to the procedures given by Lurie¹. All the other reagents used were of analytical grade.

General procedure : To a 25 ml flask, 15 ml of potassium acid phthalate buffer pH 3.1, 1 ml of 0.1% catechol, 1 ml of 0.01 N iodine and 1-5 ml of aromatic amine (concentration range, Table 1) were added in the given order. The solution was then diluted to the mark and allowed to stand at room temperature for 5-30 min (depending on the amine). At the end of this period, the absorbance was read at 500-520 nm against a reagent blank. The aromatic amine concentration was read from a calibration curve prepared with the same compound under identical conditions.

Procedure for compounds which yield primary aromatic amino group on hydrolysis : About 25 mg of the sample was boiled with 20 ml 6 N HCl for 1 hr under reflux, cooled and the excess hydrochloric acid removed under vacuum. The residue was dissolved in 50 ml of warm water and diluted to 250 ml after adjusting the pH to 5.0-7.0. The general procedure was then followed.

Procedure for compounds which yield a primary arylamino group on reduction : About 25 mg of the sample was treated with 25 ml 4 N HCl and 0.75 g zinc dust added in portions. After standing for 1 hr at room temperature, the solution was filtered through cotton wool, the residue was washed with water, excess HCl was removed and diluted to 250 ml after adjusting the pH to 5.0-7.0. The general procedure was then followed.

The sampling and preliminary treatment of dosage forms such as tablets and capsules was performed according to reported procedures^{2,3} and the assays were carried out as above depending on the nature of the compound.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves : The absorbance curves of reagent, primary arylamines and N-methylaniline show maximum absorbance at 500-520 nm; whereas catechol-iodine or primary arylamine-iodine show practically no absorption. The maximum intensity of the colour is developed within 5-20 min and is stable for 2 hr.

Effect of pH : The optimum pH range for complete colour development is 2.0-3.1 with all aromatic amines. Above pH 7.0, the colour begins to fade slowly. All studies are confined to pH 3.0 ± 0.1 .

Amount of catechol : 0.5-1.5 ml of 0.1% catechol solution is required for maximum colour development. 1 ml of 0.1% catechol was used.